

GitHub

Plugin - Changes

Plugin Tasks

01 Edit a file and open a pull request

02 From a pull request find someone to give feedback

+ Suggestions to Include in Task 2

03 Upload files into a repository

01 - Edit a file and open a pull request

Actions required to complete the task:

- 01** Click Edit > Readme File
- 02** Edit Readme File
- 03** Describe Commit Changes
- 04** Open Pull Request > Fill Pull Request Form
- 05** Complete Pull Request

01 - Click Edit > Readme File

→ **Problem:** The user has to search between the files of the repository to find Readme file and it can appear in any position. Readme file also appear below the repository files but to see that the user should scroll down to see all the page;

GenderMag Facets:

- **Learning:** by Process vs. by Tinkering;
- **Computer self-efficacy.**

The screenshot shows a GitHub repository interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs for Code, Pull requests, Actions, Projects, Wiki, Security, Insights, and Settings. Below the navigation, there's a header with 'master' branch selected, '5 branches', and '0 tags'. A 'Go to file' button and an 'Add file' button are visible. A green 'Code' button is also present. The main content area displays a list of files and folders. The file 'README.md' is highlighted with a red rectangular box. Below the file list, the content of the README file is visible, starting with the title 'ResearchPlugin' and a description: 'Chrome extension to add tooltips on GitHub pages when creating pull requests, or creating an issue report in any repository to help newcomers contribute to open source projects.' The footer of the page contains copyright information and various links like Terms, Privacy, Security, Status, Help, Contact GitHub, Pricing, API, Training, Blog, and About.

01 - Click Edit > Readme File

The screenshot shows a GitHub repository page for a file named 'README.md'. The navigation bar at the top includes a 'Home' link (highlighted with a red box), 'Code', 'Issues 3', 'Pull requests 8', 'Actions', and 'Project'. A tooltip is visible over the 'Code' tab, containing the text: 'To edit this file, go to the "code" tab above, and select the file you want to edit.' The main content area displays the README text, which includes the title 'ResearchPlugin' and a description of a Chrome extension. The right sidebar shows sections for 'About', 'Releases', and 'Packages', all of which currently show 'No [description/releases/packages] provided/published'.

Message - Tooltip: To edit this file, go to the "code" tab above, and select the file you want to edit.

- **Solution:** We highlight the importance of the Readme File into the repository hierarchy, by adding the option “Home” at nav bar, that option presents the content of this file and also include a tooltip to explain that the user can edit the file;

02 - Edit Readme File

GenderMag Facets:

- **Learning: by Process vs. by Tinkering;**
- **Computer self-efficacy;**
- **Attitude Towards Risk.**

- **Problem:** Once the user click to edit the file, it is redirected to this page where he can edit the file and fill a form to commit the changes, however for a new user is not clear that this actions are the right thing to do;

02 - Edit Readme File

→ **Message - Tooltip:** This is the file name, changing it will create a new file with the new name.

→ **Solution:**

- Include a progress bar, to indicate the steps of the workflow related to this task;
- Include a tooltip to explain what happens in case the user change the original file name;

03 - Describe Commit Changes

Commit changes

Update README.md

Add an optional extended description...

Commit directly to the `master` branch.

Create a new branch for this commit and start a pull request. [Learn more about pull requests.](#)

[Commit changes](#) [Cancel](#)

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GenderMag Facets:

- Learning: by Process vs. by Tinkering;
- Computer self-efficacy;
- Attitude Towards Risk.

- **Problem:** Here appears the commit form without any explanation and it is possible to edit the file and commit without fill it;

03 - Describe Commit Changes

- **Message - Tooltip 1:** This is the title of the pull request. Give a brief description of the change. Be short and objective.
- **Message - Tooltip 2:** Add a more detailed description of the pull request if needed. Here you can present your arguments and reasoning that lead to change.
- **Message - Tooltip 3:** By clicking the Commit Changes button the changes will automatically be pushed to the repo.

The screenshot shows the GitHub commit dialog with the following elements and annotations:

- Field Text:** A red box highlights the text "Insert a title here" in the commit title field.
- Tooltip 1:** A red label "Tooltip 1" points to a question mark icon next to the title field.
- Field Text:** A red box highlights the text "Insert a description here" in the commit description field.
- Tooltip 2:** A red label "Tooltip 2" points to a question mark icon next to the description field.
- Tooltip 3:** A red label "Tooltip 3" points to a question mark icon next to the "Commit changes" button.

Below the form, there are two radio button options:

- Commit directly to the `master` branch.
- Create a new branch for this commit and start a pull request. [Learn more about pull requests.](#)

At the bottom, there are three buttons: a question mark icon, a green "Commit changes" button, and a grey "Cancel" button.

- **Solution:** To help the user understand the importance to inform a commit message, we would put some tooltips and field text explaining the form fields;

04 - Open Pull Request

> Fill Pull Request Form

→ Solution:

- We have the progress bar, to indicate that this step is important to complete the task;
- Include a tooltip to explain the conflict message that appears;
- Include a tooltip to explain the code that is related to the changes made;

Home <> Code Pull requests Actions Projects Wiki Security Insights Settings

1 2 3
EDIT FILE CREATE PULL REQUEST PULL REQUEST OPENED

Create pull request

Finish the pull request submission below to allow others to accept the changes

base: master ← compare [dropdown]

There is a merge conflict, but this can be fixed by creating the pull request. Don't worry, the owner of the repository will fix this for you.

Write Preview H B J [dropdown] [dropdown] [dropdown] [dropdown] [dropdown] [dropdown] [dropdown] [dropdown] [dropdown] [dropdown]

Attach files by dragging & dropping, selecting or pasting them.

Create pull request

Remember, contributions to this repository should follow our GitHub Community Guidelines.

→ 1 commit 1 file changed 0 comments 1 contributor

Commits on Sep 26, 2020

Showing 1 changed file with 1 addition and 0 deletions.

1 README.md

```
@@ -5,3 +5,4 @@ This extension is written in Javascript, and uses the GitHub API to mine data ab
+
 test
 testes test
 #####
 test
```

Tooltip 1

Tooltip 2

05 - Complete Pull Request

- **Problem:** After the user click in create pull request button, it redirects to this page and do not inform if the action is completed;

GenderMag Facets:

- **Learning:** by Process vs. by Tinkering;
- **Computer Self-Efficacy;**
- **Information Processing Style.**

The screenshot displays a GitHub Pull Request interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs: Code, Pull requests (1), Actions, Projects, Wiki, Security, Insights, and Settings. The main content area shows a pull request for a C# file. The status is 'Open' and it is ready to be merged. A comment from 'italo-07' is visible. The interface includes a 'Merge pull request' button and a 'Write' section for adding a comment. The footer contains copyright information and links to Terms, Privacy, Security, Status, Help, Contact GitHub, Pricing, API, Training, Blog, and About.

05 - Complete Pull Request

→ Solution:

- After the user click in create pull request button, and it redirects to this page and a success message would appear, with progress bar showing that the task is completed;
- Include a tooltip to explain what happens in case to click in “Close pull request” button;

Message

The screenshot shows the GitHub Pull Request interface. A green success message is highlighted with a red box, indicating that the pull request was created successfully. Below the message is a progress bar with three steps: 'EDIT FILE', 'CONFIRM PULL REQUEST', and 'PULL REQUEST OPENED', all marked with green checkmarks. A tooltip is also visible, pointing to the 'Close pull request' button, with a red box around the question mark icon. The tooltip text reads: 'Remember, contributions to this repository should follow our GitHub Community Guidelines.' The main content area shows the pull request details, including the commit 'c', the branch 'patch-1-1', and the 'Merge pull request' button.

Tooltip

05 - Complete Pull Request

- **Message:** The pull request was created successfully and will be reviewed shortly;
- **Message - Tooltip 1:** This will close the pull request meaning people cannot view this! Do not click close unless the request was solved.

Message

The screenshot shows the GitHub Pull Request interface. At the top, a green message box states: "The pull request was created successfully and will be reviewed shortly". Below this, a progress bar shows three steps: "EDIT FILE", "CONFIRM PULL REQUEST", and "PULL REQUEST OPENED", all with green checkmarks. The main content area shows a comment from "italo-07" and a "Merge pull request" button. At the bottom, there is a "Close pull request" button with a tooltip icon (a question mark in a circle) next to it. The tooltip text reads: "Remember, contributions to this repository should follow our GitHub Community Guidelines." The "Close pull request" button is highlighted with a red box, and the tooltip icon is also highlighted with a red box.

Tooltip

02 - From a pull request find someone to give feedback

Actions required to complete the task:

01 Click Files Changed

01 - Click Files Changed

→ **Problem:** After the user open a pull request, it is redirected to this page and do not inform what a new user can do with the pull request created;

GenderMag Facets:

- **Learning:** by Process vs. by Tinkering;
- **Computer Self-Efficacy.**

The screenshot shows a GitHub pull request interface. At the top, there are navigation tabs for Code, Pull requests (1), Actions, Projects, Wiki, Security, Insights, and Settings. The pull request title is 'C #1' and it shows a user wants to merge 1 commit into 'master' from 'patch-1'. Below the title, there are tabs for Conversation (0), Commits (1), Checks (0), and Files changed (1). A comment from 'italo-07' is visible, stating 'c'. A status message indicates that continuous integration is not set up but that the branch has no conflicts with the base branch, allowing for an automatic merge. A 'Merge pull request' button is present. The right sidebar contains sections for Reviewers, Assignees, Labels, Projects, Milestone, Linked issues, and Notifications. The bottom of the page shows the footer with copyright information and various links.

01 - Click Files Changed

- **Solution:** Include a tooltip to highlight the nav bar that describes some actions that can be made in the pull request.
- **Message - Tooltip 1:** Feel free to explore this menu, you can discuss with project contributors, see the commits made, check the review process and see the changes made in the file related to this pull request.

The screenshot shows a GitHub pull request page for a repository named "Meu primeiro pull-request". The page title is "Meu primeiro pull-request - [redacted] # [redacted]". A green banner at the top indicates "The pull request was created successfully and will be reviewed shortly". The progress bar shows three steps: "Edit File", "Confirm Pull Request", and "Pull Request Opened", all with green checkmarks. A tooltip is displayed over the "Files changed" tab in the navigation bar, containing the text: "Feel free to explore this menu, you can discuss with project contributors, see the commits made, check the review status and see the files changed." The "Files changed" tab is highlighted with a red box. The main content area shows a comment from a user on Mar 24 with a checklist of items to check before merging. The right sidebar shows "Reviewers" (one reviewer), "Assignees" (none), "Labels" (none), and "Projects" (none).

+ Suggestions to Include in Task 2

Actions required to improve the task:

01 Mention Someone to Contribute in the Pull Request

02 Mention Someone > Click Comment

03 Confirm Mention Action

01 - Mention Someone to Contribute in the Pull Request

- **Problem:** Once the user open an issue is not clear to them that it is possible to mention someone in the comment to invite to contribute in the issue;

GenderMag Facets:

- **Learning:** by Process vs. by Tinkering;
- **Computer Self-Efficacy.**

The screenshot shows a GitHub issue page for 'teste #20'. At the top, there is a green 'Open' button and a 'New issue' button. Below the issue title, a comment from a user says 'commented 1 minute ago' with a 'new issue' button. The main content area has a 'Write' tab selected, showing a text input field with the text 'ok'. Below the input field, there is a 'Close with comment' button and a 'Comment' button. On the right side, there are sections for 'Assignees', 'Labels', 'Projects', 'Milestone', and 'Linked pull requests', all of which are currently empty or show 'None yet'. A footer note mentions the GitHub Community Guidelines.

01 - Mention Someone to Contribute in the Pull Request

teste #20

Open [user] opened this issue 1 minute ago · 0 comments

[user] commented 1 minute ago

new issue

Write Preview H B I [list] [code] [link] [table] [checkbox] [mention] [image] [undo]

ok

Attach files by dragging & dropping, selecting or pasting them.

Close with comment Comment

Remember, contributions to this repository should follow our [GitHub Community Guidelines](#).

Assignees
No one assigned

Labels
None yet

Projects
None yet

Milestone
No milestone

Linked pull requests
Successfully merging a pull request may close this issue.
None yet

→ **Solution:** Include a label in @ symbol icon to say "Use at to mention a contributor";

02 - Mention Someone > Click Comment

teste #20 Edit New issue

Open [User] opened this issue 2 minutes ago · 0 comments

[User] commented 2 minutes ago 😊 ⋮

new issue

[User]

Write Preview **H** **B** *I* **≡** **<>** **🔗** **☰** **☰** **☑** **@** **🗨** **↶**

@ [User] [User] [User] [User]

Attach files by dragging & dropping, selecting or pasting them. **📎**

Close with comment **Comment**

Remember, contributions to this repository should follow our [GitHub Community Guidelines](#).

Assignees
No one assigned

Labels
None yet

Projects
None yet

Milestone
No milestone

Linked pull requests
Successfully merging a pull request may close this issue.
None yet

Notifications Customize
Unsubscribe
You're receiving notifications because you authored the thread.

03 - Confirm Mention Action

teste #20

Open [User] opened this issue 41 minutes ago · 1 comment

[User] commented 41 minutes ago
new issue

[User] commented now
@ [User]

Write Preview H B I @

Leave a comment

Attach files by dragging & dropping, selecting or pasting them.

Close issue Comment

Remember, contributions to this repository should follow our [GitHub Community Guidelines](#).

Assignees
No one assigned

Labels
None yet

Projects
None yet

Milestone
No milestone

Linked pull requests
Successfully merging a pull request may close this issue.
None yet

Notifications [Customize](#)
[Unsubscribe](#)
You're receiving notifications because you authored the thread.

GenderMag Facets:

- Information Processing Style;
- Computer Self-Efficacy.

→ **Problem:** The mention is made and a message appear in the issue, but the user do not know what happens next;

03 - Confirm Mention Action

The screenshot shows a GitHub pull request interface. At the top, a navigation bar includes links for Home, Code, Pull requests (41), Actions, Projects, Wiki, Security, Insights, and Settings. A green banner with a red border contains the message: "The mentioned user will receive a notification and may help you work on the pull request." Below this, a progress bar shows three steps: "Edit File", "Confirm Pull Request", and "Pull Request Opened", each with a green checkmark. The pull request title is "Meu primeiro pull-request - [redacted] #110". A green "Open" button is visible. Below the title, a comment from a "First-time contributor" lists several checklist items: "Change in CHANGELOG.md described (if applicable)", "Tests created for changes (if applicable)", "Manually tested changed features in running JabRef (always required)", "Screenshots added in PR description (for UI changes)", and "Checked documentation: Is the information available and up to date? If not created an issue at <https://github.com/JabRef/user-documentation/issues> or, even better, submitted a pull request to the documentation repository." Below the comment, a commit "Update README.md" is shown as "Verified". Another comment from the "Owner" asks "Can you help me?". On the right side, there are sections for "Reviewers", "Suggestions", "Assignees", "Labels", "Projects", and "Milestone", each with a gear icon for settings.

→ **Message:** The mentioned user will receive a notification and may help you to work on the pull request;

→ **Solution:** To improve that, we include a confirmation message to let the user know that the contributor mentioned will receive a notification and may help the newcomer in this issue.

03 - Upload files into a repository

Actions required to complete the task:

- 01** Click Add File > Upload Files
- 02** Confirm Fork Action
- 03** Click Add Files > Upload Files
- 04** Upload File and Fill Commit Form
- 05** Complete Upload Files

01 - Click Add File > Upload Files

The screenshot shows a GitHub repository page. At the top, there are navigation tabs: Home, Code, Issues (2), Pull requests (5), Actions, Projects, Wiki, Security, and Insights. Below the navigation, there's a section for the current branch, 'master', with 4 branches and 0 tags. A 'Merge pull request #2 from [redacted] master' button is visible. To the right of the merge button, there are three buttons: 'Go to file', 'Add file', and 'Code'. The 'Add file' button is highlighted with a red box, and its dropdown menu is open, showing two options: 'Create new file' and 'Upload files'. Below the buttons, there's a table of files in the repository:

File Name	Description	Time Ago
Chart.bundle.js	Updated progress bar and created graphs in promie page	3 months ago
README.md	Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar	2 months ago
background.js	Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar	2 months ago
content.js	Updated styles, code readability and added api graph on profile page	2 months ago
index.html	Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar	2 months ago
jquery.min.js	finally got the simple jquery working.	5 months ago
manifest.json	Updated styles, code readability and added api graph on profile page	2 months ago

On the right side of the page, there are sections for 'About', 'Releases', and 'Packages'. The 'About' section has a note: 'No description, website, or topics provided.' The 'Releases' section says 'No releases published.' The 'Packages' section says 'No packages published.'

01 - Click Add Files > Upload Files

- **Problem:** It is not possible to upload a file, because the newcomer didn't have forked the repository, and the interface do not help informing what to do;

GenderMag Facets:

- **Information Processing Style;**
- **Attitude Towards Risk;**
- **Motivations.**

01 - Click Add Files > Upload Files

- **Solution:** Change the message to inform that is necessary to fork and make the fork button green to highlight that it is enabled;

02 - Confirm Fork Action

→ **Problem:** Once the user click in the fork button, it redirects to repository page and do not inform if the action is completed;

GenderMag Facets:

- **Information Processing Style;**
- **Computer Self-Efficacy.**

02 - Confirm Fork Action

→ **Message:** The repository was successfully forked, feel free to contribute and add new files;

→ **Solution:** Once the user click in the fork button, and it redirects to repository page a success message would appear;

03 - Click Add Files > Upload Files

The screenshot shows the GitHub repository interface. At the top, there are navigation links: Home, Code, Issues (2), Pull requests (5), Actions, Projects, Wiki, Security, and Insights. Below the navigation, there are repository details: master branch, 4 branches, and 0 tags. A red box highlights the 'Add file' dropdown menu, which is open and shows two options: 'Create new file' and 'Upload files'. The 'Upload files' option is selected. Below the dropdown, there is a table of files in the repository:

File Name	Description	Last Commit
Chart.bundle.js	Updated progress bar and created graphs in profile page	3 months ago
README.md	Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar	2 months ago
background.js	Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar	2 months ago
content.js	Updated styles, code readability and added api graph on profile page	2 months ago
index.html	Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar	2 months ago
jquery.min.js	finally got the simple jquery working.	5 months ago
manifest.json	Updated styles, code readability and added api graph on profile page	2 months ago

On the right side of the interface, there are sections for 'About' (No description, website, or topics provided), 'Readme', 'Releases' (No releases published), and 'Packages' (No packages published).

04 - Upload File and Fill Commit Form

- **Problem:** Here appears the commit form without any explanation and it is possible to upload the file without fill it;

GenderMag Facets:

- **Learning:** by Process vs. by Tinkering;
- **Motivations.**

The screenshot shows the GitHub web interface for a repository named 'ResearchPlugin'. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, Code, Pull requests, Actions, Projects, Wiki, Security, Insights, and Settings. Below the navigation bar, the repository name 'ResearchPlugin /' is displayed. The main content area features a large white box with a light gray border containing a drag-and-drop area. Inside this box, there are icons for a document, a bar chart, a code editor, a list, and a folder. Below the icons, the text reads 'Drag files here to add them to your repository' and 'Or choose your files'. Below the drag-and-drop area, there is a 'Commit changes' section. This section includes a text input field labeled 'Add files via upload', a larger text area labeled 'Add an optional extended description...', and two radio button options: 'Commit directly to the master branch.' (which is selected) and 'Create a new branch for this commit and start a pull request. Learn more about pull requests.'. At the bottom of the 'Commit changes' section, there are two buttons: 'Commit changes' (in green) and 'Cancel'. The footer of the page contains copyright information for GitHub, Inc. and various links like Terms, Privacy, Security, Status, Help, Contact GitHub, Pricing, API, Training, Blog, and About.

04 - Upload File and Fill Commit Form

The screenshot shows the GitHub web interface for a repository named 'ResearchPlugin'. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, Code, Pull requests, Actions, Projects, Wiki, Security, Insights, and Settings. Below the navigation bar, the repository name 'ResearchPlugin /' is displayed. The main content area features a large box with the text 'Drag files here to add them to your repository' and 'Or choose your files'. Below this, there is a 'Commit changes' form. The form has two input fields: 'Add files via upload' and 'Add an optional extended description...'. There are two red callout boxes labeled 'Tooltip 1' and 'Tooltip 2' pointing to the first and second input fields respectively. The tooltip text reads: 'This is the title of the commit. Give a brief description of the change. Be short and objective.' Below the input fields, there are two radio buttons: 'Commit directly to the master branch.' (selected) and 'Create a new branch for this commit and start a pull request. Learn more about pull requests.' At the bottom of the form, there are two buttons: 'Commit changes' (green) and 'Cancel' (white). The footer of the page contains copyright information and various links.

- **Solution:** To make the newcomer understand the importance to inform a commit message, we would put some tooltips explaining the form fields, similar to pull request task;
- **Message - Tooltip 1:** This is the title of the commit. Give a brief description of the change. Be short and objective.
- **Message - Tooltip 2:** Add a more detailed description of the commit if needed. Here you can describe the files uploaded.

05 - Complete Upload File

- **Problem:** Once the user click in commit changes button, it redirects to repository page and do not inform if the action is completed, it only appear the message: **This branch is 5 commits ahead of NAU-OSL:master;**

GenderMag Facets:

- **Information Processing Style;**
- **Learning: by Process vs. by Tinkering.**

The screenshot shows a GitHub repository page for a user named 'NAU-OSL'. The page is on the 'Code' tab, showing the 'master' branch with 4 branches and 0 tags. A red box highlights the message 'This branch is 5 commits ahead of NAU-OSL:master'. Below this, there is a list of files and their commit history. The files listed are: Chart.bundle.js, README.md, background.js, content.js, index.html, jquery.min.js, manifest.json, outline.png, popup.js, result.json, styles.css, and test.txt. The commit history for each file shows the commit message and the time since the last commit. For example, 'Chart.bundle.js' was last committed 3 months ago with the message 'Updated progress bar and created graphs in profile page'. The 'test.txt' file was last committed 18 minutes ago with the message 'Add files via upload'. The page also includes navigation links for Home, Code, Pull requests, Actions, Projects, Wiki, Security, Insights, and Settings. On the right side, there are sections for About, Releases, Packages, and Languages. The footer contains copyright information for GitHub, Inc. and various links like Terms, Privacy, Security, Status, Help, Contact GitHub, Pricing, API, Training, Blog, and About.

05 - Complete Upload File

The screenshot shows the GitHub repository page for a user. A green success message is highlighted with a red box: "The repository was successfully forked, feel free to contribute and add new files." Below this message is a table of files in the repository. The table has columns for file name, commit message, and time ago. The files listed are: Chart.bundle.js, README.md, background.js, content.js, index.html, jquery.min.js, manifest.json, outline.png, popup.js, result.json, and styles.css. The commit messages are: "Updated progress bar and created graphs in profile page", "Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar", "Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar", "Updated styles, code readability and added api graph on profile page", "Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar", "finally got the simple jquery working.", "Updated styles, code readability and added api graph on profile page", "Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar", "Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar", "Updated styles, code readability and added api graph on profile page", and "Updated styles, code readability and added api graph on profile page". The commit times range from 2 months ago to 5 months ago. The repository has 4 branches and 0 tags. The page also shows sections for About, Releases, Packages, and Languages. The Languages section shows a bar chart with JavaScript at 82.7%, CSS at 10.1%, and HTML at 7.2%.

File Name	Commit Message	Time Ago
Chart.bundle.js	Updated progress bar and created graphs in profile page	3 months ago
README.md	Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar	2 months ago
background.js	Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar	2 months ago
content.js	Updated styles, code readability and added api graph on profile page	2 months ago
index.html	Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar	2 months ago
jquery.min.js	finally got the simple jquery working.	5 months ago
manifest.json	Updated styles, code readability and added api graph on profile page	2 months ago
outline.png	Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar	2 months ago
popup.js	Updated graph, icon text, and progress bar	2 months ago
result.json	Updated styles, code readability and added api graph on profile page	2 months ago
styles.css	Updated styles, code readability and added api graph on profile page	2 months ago

→ **Solution:** Once the user click in the commit changes button, and it redirects to repository page and a success message would appear;

→ **Message:** The files were successfully added;

GitHub

Plugin - Changes